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operational problems, solutions and technical practices via
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European Investigation Order: Favor cooperationis, operational problems, solutions and technical practices via the report of the Eurojust

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Abstract: This work aims to make a summary of the problems created through the European Investigation Order (EIO) and of how they are collected from the first report we saw from Eurojust at the end of 2020. It is a new system within the European Union which allowed us to highlight not so much theoretical problems but practical and technical ones that deal with telecommunications interceptions, transfer of prisoners, linguistic and translation problems as well as the examination of witnesses. Many problems are still exist. A lot of work done, but still in the process of developing a very complicated work of a supranational, European nature which goes beyond the limits of national law. National criminal procedural help certainly provided answers but in some cases the issues remained

unresolved. The clarifications are still lacking a total answer because as was foreseen and as expected, each new system takes a long time to improve the procedural process, evidential in the European context as new challenges that we see in the coming years are in continuous evolution through reforms and modifications.

Keywords: EIO; European criminal harmonization; technical problems; operational problems of investigations; report of the Eurojust; telecommunications interceptions; coordination problems; European criminal procedural law; European Union law; European criminal cooperation; European harmonization.

Introduction: Purpose and objectives of the Eurojust report

Carefully reading the first Eurojust report of 10 November 2020 regarding the use of the European Investigation Order (EIO) in the context of European judicial cooperation and particularly in the evidentiary field makes us think about the problems created, those solved and the future challenges in this sector¹. As we understand, the problems are connected with the practice of applying this instrument as is also possible every time a new form of cooperation to be established and as we have noted this

¹<https://www.Eurojust.europa.eu/it/publication/report-Eurojust-casework-european-investigation-order>

reality also applies not only at European but also at national level, highlighting not only the problems but also the attempt, the political and administrative desire to overcome the obstacles encountered by encouraging collaboration between the authorities of the Member States.

The preamble of the Directive 2014/41/EU (Mangiaracina, 2014; Ruggeri, 2014)² and the recital n. 13 show an involvement of the issuing procedures and the related execution of the EIO thus constituting a good outcome to the cooperation. The national authorities involved at the European Union Agency for Criminal Justice Cooperation (EUACJC) also in the phase prior to the issuing of the EIO with the aim of obtaining information or evaluating the opportunities to adopt the relevant single order and/or to divide it according to the requests of the first objective that they want to achieve, namely:

“(...) the choice between issuing one single EIO and splitting it into several EIOs (...)” (Airapetean, Corsei, Stefanoaia, 2021).

The experience of the evidentiary device has already emerged since 2018 after the first experiences in the sector and after the first meetings relating to the issuing of the relevant joint note between Eurojust and the European Judicial Network of June 2019, thus providing information and guidelines relating to the application of the instrument in examining and highlighting the

²Directive 2014/41/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 3 April 2014 regarding the European Investigation Order in criminal matters, OJ L 130, 1.5.2014, p. 1-36.

first problems, challenges and unresolved practices in the field of criminal justice cooperation³.

According to the report of 2020, from a structural point of view we note:

“(...) the essence of Eurojust's role, of simplification (facilitation), support and strengthening of coordination and cooperation (coordination), and then offering (...) an overview of the results obtained from the analysis of the multiple cases managed and some practical suggestions (...) on the main difficulties that have arisen in relation to specific investigative measures, from the temporary transfer of prisoners to undercover operations, paying particular attention to the relevant discipline to the hearing via videoconference and to wiretaps, the latter being a source of novelty and, at the same time, interpretative problems (...)” (Navickaitė, 2016).

The general nature of the EIO is the first part of the relationship introducing as a replacement objective the improvement of a regulatory framework regarding mutual criminal legal assistance. The standards we have in our hands are the growing role of the judicial authorities and the provision of limited reasons for refusal and time limits that determine the relevant instrument of evidence collection, producing a positive path on criminal cooperation.

Within this first framework, the principle of mutual recognition is very important, which in a concrete and indispensable way guides to a correct interpretation of the relative reasons for non-recognition of the supranational legislation, as well as the temporal problem involving the issuing and execution procedures (Kuzak, 2019).

³www.eurojus.europa.eu.

What are the main issues according to the casework examined by the national desks at the EUACJC? To answer this question we must first examine which are the relevant issues that involve the main problems, namely: the scope of application of the relevant directive; the method of completing the sections in the attached forms; to understand the gaps that exist between national regulations; the interpretation of a stringent nature for the reasons for denying these modules; to make the enforcement system of the EIO more rapid and concrete, thus identifying that cases requiring urgent treatment also allow the facilitation of work by involving Eurojust through a direct exchange of information between the relevant authorities; the use of the forms in annexes B) and C) of the directive; identify the execution and competent to transmit the EIO; coordinate in an overall manner the execution of the EIO in various Member States and with legal assistance tools. As can be understood, we are faced with a list of problems of a more practical and non-substantial nature which are oriented towards the acquisition of cross-border evidence, thus contributing to the mechanism of mutual recognition in the evidentiary field:

“(...) the report clearly indicates that the EIO is not functioning as a well-oiled machine (...)”⁴.

⁴<https://www.Eurojust.europa.eu/it/publication/report-Eurojust-casework-european-investigation-order>

The report delves into and identifies the solutions of good practices by putting the application experience to the demonstrative reference that the EIO base on the principle of mutual recognition. This is not a magical compilation map because it lacks clarity of exposition and retraces some general problems that are actually selected by Eurojust and are dedicated for investigation and deeper reflection.

The application of the Directive 2014/41/EU

When we talk about the application of the Directive 2014/41/EU we are referring to its practical subjective and objective nature. From an objective point of view, the difficulties lie in the borderline between police and judicial cooperation, distinguishing the cases that resort to the EIO. The covert investigations and the cross-border surveillance according to the recital 9 of the directive affirms that:

“(...) the implementing Convention of the Schengen Agreement⁵ should continue to operate (...)”.

⁵See the Joint Note of Eurojust and the European Judicial Network on the practical application of the European Investigation Order, dated June 2019: www.Eurojust.europa.eu, p. 23: “(...) most Member States consider that cross-border observations form part of police cooperation and that it is not appropriate to issue an EIO in these cases. For other Member States they fall under judicial cooperation. Some Member States have also clarified that cross-border observations do not fall within the scope of the EIO unless the procedure involves the use of monitoring devices, geo-location and/or eaves dropping. Different interpretations of the scope of the EIO regarding cross-border observations can create problems. One issue concerns the limitation of the use of evidence obtained through cross-border observations: in some Member States the evidence collected through this measure can be used before a court, while in other Member States this is not possible (...)”.

The relationships between the EIO and the other cooperation instruments, such as the European arrest warrant, the transfer of persons detained from one Member State to another, the preventive seizure and confiscation measures of assets, the distinction between the aforementioned instruments, although clear on a theoretical level, tend to fade significantly in practice. It is not always easy to identify the objective pursued by the request coming from abroad. This happens in cases where the transfer of a person is preordained for the exercise of criminal action (purpose of prosecution) or upon completion of an investigation (purpose of evidence gathering) or, with reference to the final destination of the seized asset, whether the seizure is requested for evidentiary purposes only (freezing for evidence gathering) or with a view to future confiscation (freezing for confiscation) (Liakopoulos, 2020; Phil, 2022)⁶.

A joint, complementary use of multiple cooperation tools is necessary. Within the general spirit of good practice as synonymous with good faith, the compilation of the section D) of the form which is part of the annex A) of the directive is aware of the change in the purposes and objectives of the same as well as the possibility of proceeding with the confiscation of the seized assets or to proceed with their return to the person

⁶See the Regulation (EU) 2018/1805 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 November 2018 on the mutual recognition of freezing orders and confiscation orders, PE/38/2018/REV/1, OJ L 303, 28.11.2018, p. 1–38.

entitled to them. We note how perplexed and obscure the relationship between the EIO and the joint investigation team is, given that in practice it was left without any sensational cooperation work after the entry into force of the directive (Espina Ramos, 2019; Billet, Turmo, 2020).

Between issuing a European investigation order and setting up the relevant team for the evaluation of previous authorities depends on the peculiarities of each concrete case. The establishment of an investigative team for the acquisition of evidence within the scope of the same are excluded from the operational sphere of the EIO directive and in several cases are characterized by the relative complexities experienced between the synergy of the tools. In this sector we remember Art. 34, par. 1 of the Directive 2014/41/EU which provides/states: “(...) the replacement, by the directive itself, of the

“corresponding provisions” contained in (...) 1959 and in the two additional protocols, in the Convention implementing the Schengen Agreement and in the Brussels Convention of 2000 between the Member States of the European Union and in the related protocol (...) the restitution to the person injured by the crime of theft of a racehorse. The issuing authority turned to Eurojust to clarify whether the request concerning the seizure and transport of the animal fell within the scope of the EIO or that of the rogatory letters (...). The executing authority, made possible thanks to the intermediation of Eurojust (...) and an EIO relating to the hearing of the person who was in possession of it (...)”⁷.

Although Denmark and Ireland have decided to remain outside the directive by relying on the opt-out mechanism, many times

⁷CJEU, C-16/22, Staatsanwaltschaft Graz (Service des affaires fiscales pénales de Düsseldorf) of 02 March 2023, ECLI:EU:C:2023:148, not yet published.

they have received investigation orders relating to rogatory letters either by mistake or ignorance. These states show a flexible attitude given that they have informed Eurojust of their willingness to treat the orders received as if they were rogatory letters.

What are the problems in compiling Annex A)?

One of the major problems that the report of 2020 noted was the late execution and transmission of insufficient information in an incomplete, contradictory manner regarding the crucial aspects which have as their object the reasons for the request as well as the description of the crime fact which proceeds the indication of the investigative act to be carried out as provided for by Art. 5 of the Directive.

The majority of cases in Annex A) are left blank or filled in incorrectly, thus allowing Eurojust to clarify and answer questions to facilitate the exchange of additional documentation. It is normal that Eurojust found itself faced with a difficult reality given that in practice it had to clarify and provide information on cases that were not precise in relation to national regulations for the legal qualification of the fact.

Regarding section G) which was dedicated to the descriptive facts of the crimes included or the circumstances of the crime. The intervention of the Eurojust gave light to the authorities

issuing information that was missing or was specific to certain investigative measures requested, even those that had to do with the suspect or witness and did not contain sufficient elements to allow the enforcement authorities to trace persons who lacked important information regarding certain persons as suspects or witnesses and the manner in which the examination was carried out.

Regarding the seizure and house search, information was found with errors, for example incomplete forms from the bank account to the home address to be searched are noted. Telephone interceptions also do not fall outside this framework, which Eurojust very carefully called:

“(...) of the issuing authority the importance of explicitly indicating the existence of a connection between the telephone number to be intercepted and the facts which are the subject of the proceedings, the necessity and proportionality of the requested measure, as well as the indication of the duration of the operations and any extensions (...) compare with requests that appeared superfluous, specious and, as such, not justified in the context of cooperation based on mutual trust and recognition (...). The executing authority requested to be able to examine the entire file of the proceedings initiated in the issuing state. The issuing authority initially opposed this request, arguing that it was contrary to the fundamental principles underlying the EIO Directive, but, fearing that otherwise the order would remain unexecuted, declared itself willing to allow access (...)”⁸.

Thus it is understood that Eurojust carried out the orders which were partially correct and the competent authorities of the Member States involved planned meetings with the aim of developing structural solutions to requests which in reality were

⁸CJEU, C-724/19 Spetsializirana prokuratura () e à la localisation) of 16 December 2021, ECLI:EU:C:2021:1020, not yet published.

without substance.

What was interesting was the connection of the investigations for Islamic terrorism, thus showing that the requests of the executing authority were to acquire information that respects that already received, thus resolving an obstacle for the effective criminal judicial cooperation. In practice, the sending of the issuing authority of detailed information regarding the existing evidence against a suspect and the related elements showing the social dangerousness leads to the execution of refusing recognition of the order based on an insufficient procedure of acquired elements and as a consequence the denial of discretionary assessments which conflict with the principle of mutual recognition according to the spirit of the Directive.

What happens regarding the relevant sections L) and J) of the annex A)?

The relevant sections L) and J) of the annex A) concern the data of the validating judicial authority of the EIO and the related means of appeal which were available in the issuing state but left blank in practice.

The execution of coercive investigative measures which included house searches and telephone interceptions, Eurojust states that:

“(…) to order the decision of the national authority authorizing the requested act, although Art. 5 of the Directive does not expressly prescribe it (…)

noted both the failure to complete the aforementioned section and the failure to send a copy of the provision authorizing the operations, which was sent subsequently, upon explicit request of the executing authority (...) the national desk of the executing Member State-not named in the report-has proposed two alternative solutions: the compilation of the “L” section, with signature of the authority that authorized the interception, or the attachment of the authorization provision translated into the language of the country of destination (...)”⁹.

Instead, as regards section J) the main problems were oriented towards the indication that:

“(...) has already been used to appeal against the issuance of an EIO and, in informative cases, to provide further details (...) the Luxembourg judges clarified that Art. 5 par. 1 of the Directive must be interpreted as meaning that the judicial authority of a Member State, when issuing an EIO, is not required to provide, in section “J”, a description of the legal remedies available in that state, the communication of the appeal against the provision of recognition or execution of the order being sufficient, in accordance with the provisions of art. 14 par. 7 (...)”¹⁰ (Siracusano, 2019).

Section I) and the procedural systems of the individual Member States

As regards section I) we are dealing with the criminal procedural and evidentiary sector through the national regulations where the EIO, comparable with the system of rogatory letters, inserted a context which was characterized by the absence of preventive harmonization in relation to procedural rules of admissibility and usability of the tests. The objective of the directive in this sector was the simplicity, precision and speed of cooperation through orders with

⁹<https://www.Eurojust.europa.eu/it/publication/report-Eurojust-casework-european-investigation-order>

¹⁰<https://www.Eurojust.europa.eu/it/publication/report-Eurojust-casework-european-investigation-order>

uncomplicated content which distinguish the procedural systems between the various Member States.

Art. 9, par. 2 of the Directive states:

“(...) the formalities and procedures expressly indicated by the issuing authority which the executing authority must comply with, unless they conflict with the fundamental principles of the *lex loci* (...) reflects the need to create an approximation between the regulations of the individual Member States of the European Union, as already desired by Art. 82 par. 2 TFEU, with the aim of facilitating judicial cooperation in criminal matters. In view of this objective, it is clear that a correct and exhaustive compilation of section “I”, reserved for the indication of the forms and procedures required for the execution of the order, constitutes the prerequisite for valid collaboration. Only compliance with such formalities on the part of the issuing authority, where possible, can in fact ensure the usability of the evidentiary material collected aliunde (...)”¹¹ (Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021).

Many times and according to the report it was noted that section I) was omitted and the necessary information was collected after relative zeal by Eurojust. And we say this given that in the case of a witness as a subject to be examined he had to be informed of his rights in a precise manner as well as to the competent authorities who receive the statements. Neglecting the checks of the orders relating to the interrogation of the person who was under investigation was an argument in *commis* which we also saw in the related questions addressed to the person to be subjected to the first hearing and with the related recognition of the *lex fori*. Investigations whether they included witnesses or not are introduced through the judicial or police authorities included in the order and communicated through Eurojust in an

¹¹<https://www.Eurojust.europa.eu/it/publication/report-Eurojust-casework-european-investigation-order>

urgent manner before the hearing takes place in the executing state as a participatory authority. Declarations made before the executing authority through a lawyer are unusable according to the *lex fori*.

All this happens due to national procedural regulations and to different interpretations that the same directive invoked by individual states to justify the impossibility of carrying out specific investigative measures, such as the interception of telecommunications and the temporary transfer of prisoners and cross-border observations. Such a provision referred to in Art. 31 par. 3 of the Directive on interceptions without the technical assistance of another Member State, to which we will return later, in relation to which there is no unanimity of opinion regarding the meaning to be attributed to the expression “if the interception is not admitted in a similar internal case”. It is anticipated that the orientations oscillate between those who believe it is necessary to carry out an extended check on the existence of the admissibility conditions established by the *lex loci* and those who, instead, affirm that the notified state must limit itself to a formal assessment, i.e. limited to the correspondence of the crime for which the wiretaps are ordered¹².

¹²CJEU, C-180/21, *Inspektor v Inspektorata kam Visshia sadeben savet* (Finalités du traitement de données - Enquête pénale), of 08 December 2021, ECLI:EU:C.2021:967, not yet published. C-338/21, *Staatssecretaris van Justitie en Veiligheid (Délai de transfert - Traite des êtres humains)* of 30 March 2023,

Dissemination at a supranational level is achieved by inserting precise and unambiguous definitions into the text of the directive, avoiding the usability of tests taken abroad.

(Follows). The principle of specialty

The rule of specialty has not been inserted anywhere except in art. 22, par. 8 (Barbosa e Silva, 2019) which concerned the temporary transfer of prisoners used material that was collected by the national authorities. Evidence taken in the executing state can also be used in proceedings that are different from the one or those that were issued at the EIO. We are faced with a lot of questions to ask in this type of collaboration of evidence, such as evidence for all types of crimes and especially in the sector of fraud which concerned pensions and funds acquired from various Member States of the EU. In this case the investigations included an enormous amount of work between rogatory letters and EIO in a direct manner between the member countries, thus revealing that the qualified facts relating to the damage of a state had to integrate the details which amounted to a pure case of fraud also involving other crimes concerning money laundering and corruption through archiving cases and/or registering new investigations. The granting of evidence through authorization in relation to certain different crimes remains in the same initial

ECLI:EU:C:2023:269, not yet published.

request which was necessary and specific and accepted after a request from the issuing authority to extend the usability of the evidence up to the time of its collection.

Double criminality and ne bis in idem

Some of the reasons for denial of the EIO were the grounds for non-recognition or for non-execution and everything that included this practice. The related consultation between the relevant authorities and the appropriate decisions regarding the executability of the order also unfortunately allowed the issuing of new orders and then being executed successfully or not.

According to the report of the 2020 in this sector:

“(…) the issues related to the alleged violation of the principle of double criminality and ne bis in idem were far more frequent than those related to the other reasons for refusal contemplated by Art. 11 of the Directive”.

Two specific problems that involve the principle of double criminality deserve to be mentioned. On several occasions the executing authorities have invoked the reason for refusal based on double criminality also in relation to those investigative measures (privileged measures) for which, as can be seen from the combined provisions of Articles 10 par. 2 and 11 par. 2 of the EIO Directive, it should not operate. The investigative measures “which must always be available” include, by way of example, the hearing of a witness, a person under investigation or a defendant and “non-coercive” investigative measures, the

identification of which, in the absence of a specific definition in the text of the Directive, is left to the discretion of the executing state. In such cases, the execution of the EIO required the intervention of Eurojust, to clarify that the measures indicated by Art. 10 par. 2 of the Directive must always be considered available in the executing state, even if the fact being prosecuted does not constitute a crime on the basis of the *lex loci*. The originally refused refusal has been withdrawn and, consequently, the order¹³.

A related problem was connected with the list of the annex D) of the EIO Directive, i.e. the offenses list which took into consideration the seriousness, the fulfillment of the condition of double criminality, as well as the commission of a crime as a prerequisite (predicate offence) that has to do with money laundering and participation in a criminal organization. The executing authorities thus refused the recognition of the EIO and placed the crime as a prerequisite which passed the test of double criminality.

Double criminality was also noted in cases where the transmission of an EIO obtained documents that were related to a proceeding initiated in the executing state. The executing authority thus did not intend to provide requested documentation

¹³<https://www.Eurojust.europa.eu/it/publication/report-Eurojust-casework-european-investigation-order>, see also: CJEU, C-435/22 PPU, Generalstaatsanwaltschaft München and ne bis in idem) of 13 October 2022, ECLI:EU:C:2022:852, not yet published.

based on the fear that its use by the issuing authority would lead to a violation of the principle of ne bis in idem. According to Eurojust, these documents could be used:

“(...) solely to close the proceedings in the issuing state. Therefore, the order was promptly executed (...)”¹⁴.

The reason for non-recognition in relation to immunities or privileges, even of a professional nature, are difficulties that reports are summarized and based on banking secrecy, diplomatic immunities and a procedure which concerned the return to the person entitled for the search in the relevant offices or not of the person as a suspect.

Within this framework, the national authorities turn to Eurojust with the aim of evaluating the execution of the relevant orders issued for minor crimes, i.e. petty offenses, through an alternative type of investigation, less invasive than the one requested, also carrying out wiretaps through the EIO telephone calls, acquisition of bank documents to ascertain frauds with a value of approximately 2000 euros. Thus, according to the executing authority:

“(...) the requests received, given the small amount of damage done to the assets, contacted Eurojust to discuss the practicable options”.

On this occasion, the possibility, initially considered, of invoking the reason for refusal referred to in Art. 11 § 1 letter. h) of the EIO Directive, reserved for cases in which the

¹⁴<https://www.Eurojust.europa.eu/it/publication/report-Eurojust-casework-european-investigation-order>

performance of the requested act is limited by the *lex loci* to a certain category of crimes or to crimes punishable within a certain threshold. The punishability of fraud in the executing state was regardless of the entity of the profit achieved and, therefore, the order was executed¹⁵.

A balance between investigative or evidentiary needs and the related fundamental guarantees of the procedure raises many doubts relating to the obligations incumbent on the executing state according to Art. 6 TEU and of the Charter of the Fundamental Rights of the European Union (CFREU) (Blanke, Mangiamelli, 2021).

According to our opinion the biggest problem was the presumed incompatibility with the guarantees envisaged of a supranational nature and according to the different methods where the legal systems respect the Member States and were oriented towards the protection of fundamental rights where the order is thus executed after having provided the executing authority a detailed description of the procedural guarantees that are recognized by the issuing state (Armada, 2015).

The role of Eurojust in speeding up cooperation procedures

The acceleration of cooperation procedures occupies a significant part of the mediation work carried out by Eurojust,

¹⁵<https://www.Eurojust.europa.eu/it/publication/report-Eurojust-casework-european-investigation-order>

especially in relation to urgent procedures and “forgotten EIOs” by the executing authorities.

In numerous cases, the intervention of the EUACJC has allowed a rapid execution of the orders, providing the authorities involved with some clarifications relating to theoretical or practical aspects. Often, the requested information or evidence had to be obtained within a few days or even a few hours. In the majority of these cases, Eurojust managed to ensure the execution of the EIO within the set deadline.

With regard to urgent procedures, there has sometimes been an improper use by the issuing authorities of section “B” of Annex “A”, where it is requested to specify the reasons for which the urgency is considered to exist. Often, in fact, the appropriate space is blacked out even if the completion of the investigation is not really urgent or left blank when, on the contrary, a rapid fulfillment of the order would be appropriate. Eurojust intervened to provide clarification regarding the urgent nature of certain investigative measures, which is not clearly deducible from the content of the EIO. In this regard, it is recommended that operators, as good practice, promptly justify the reasons for the urgency of the requested act, whenever the relevant urgency box is ticked. The reasons that lead to qualifying the completion of an act as urgent can be the most disparate. Think of the hypothesis in which the person under investigation is subjected

to the execution of precautionary custodial measures, or the existence of an imminent danger of destruction of the evidence or, again, to the particular gravity of the crime for which proceedings are being carried out in the issuing state.

In the absence of justified reasons to support the urgency, section “B” should, however, be left out.

What happens regarding communication problems between the authorities involved?

The communication problem was linked not only to linguistic difficulties but also to the lack of responses from the relevant enforcement authorities and the failure to use the relevant order confirmation form according to Annex B). Also in this case, Eurojust intervened to promote a certain direct, precise contact with the authorities, thus facilitating the exchange of necessary information. There was no trace or form where Annex B) comes from the issuing authority. The relationships between the authorities are concentrated on requests for additional information, thus requesting the sending of Annex B) as a use of solutions in favor of the authorities involved and according to the methods of execution of the EIO. The executing authority limited itself to expressing the relative refusal without obviously providing a response to the relative requests with explanations to the issuing authority, thus opposing the execution of specific

investigative measures where according to Art. 10, par. 2 of the Directive had to be available. In this case the Eurojust tried to re-establish contacts between the authorities involved and, secondarily, to understand the reasons for the refusal and verify whether there was room to overcome them, leading thus to the execution or, on the contrary, upon confirmation to the denial. Despite the intervention of the Agency, no explanation justifying the refusal was ever received. Only a partial execution of the order was happened. The authorities contacted Eurojust to identify and overcome the obstacles that prevented its full implementation. Connected to that was the withdrawal of “defective” orders, i.e. affected by formal and content anomalies or errors which cannot be rectified even with the intervention of Eurojust. There was no correspondence, in terms of content, between the request made by a defender, who asked for a judge to carry out the examination of a witness, and the form referred to in Annex “A”, which indicated the judicial police as the competent body for carrying out the act. In these cases, sometimes, the only way out consists in withdrawing the defective order and issuing a new one¹⁶.

The differences between national legislation in the procedural and evidentiary fields reveal themselves as misunderstandings and represent a relative temporal obstacle for cooperative

¹⁶<https://www.Eurojust.europa.eu/it/publication/report-Eurojust-casework-european-investigation-order>

effectiveness. In this case we can remember the cross-border trafficking of narcotics, where the interception of one's conversations has put under the microscope the use of means not always used for the use of transporting narcotic substances. In this case the problem was on the one hand the difficulty in carrying out the measures and the *lex loci* which required punishability respecting that provided by the *lex fori* as well as the application of domestic law.

What are the problems associated with language difficulties?

The linguistic problem was commented on and used positively and negatively within the EU many years ago. The problem was not so much the accurate translation but the unjustified delay. Incomprehensible traditions created not by professionals and by those who had legal linguistic knowledge but through Google Translate put the translation as having no qualitative value, superficial, incomplete thus forcing the national desks to provide a priori and in a timely manner the relevant translation into English for the EIO with a flexible approach where most states were to begin the execution of orders that were urgent, issued in other languages except English as a practice not recommended, but necessary especially as regards the issuing and signing of orders in the original language. Thus Eurojust also favored the relevant agreements regarding translation without exceeding the

related costs.

Competent enforcement authority and transmission channels

The linguistic problem was only the basis for the opening of another problem relating to the execution of decisions as well as the identification of transmission in the issuing authorities and to the authorities at the same time.

The relevant appeals by each state, the different criteria for designating the authorities responsible for the execution, the investigation for the crime of child pornography on websites and the identification of the IP address forced the suspect to carry out the relevant searches inside the home following the tracing of the first authority, forwarding afterwards and through Eurojust to carry out the house search.

Eurojust preferred to follow the correct identification to the competent authorities and to send it to a single EIO and to different prosecutors. The transmission channel was that of the SIENA (Secure Information Exchange Network Application), as a specific platform of the Europol for the communication needs of the police forces. Pursuant to Art. 7 § 6 of the Directive, the authority without competence which nevertheless receives an order is required to transmit it ex officio to the one deemed competent, giving simultaneous notice to the issuing authority.

The issuing states have repeatedly asked Eurojust if it was necessary to also send by post a paper copy of the order already sent via email. In June 2017, the Estonia desk raised an operational question on the use of digital tools, which also touched on the aspect relating to the identification of cases in which the transmission of an EIO (or a letter rogatory) electronically (email or fax) was sufficient and of those which, instead, also required the sending of a paper copy by post. They have revealed that the majority of Member States accept the digital version of an EIO and specified that, although the execution of the EIO received by email or fax can be started, subsequent transmission by post is still necessary¹⁷.

Identification is also connected with the sector of confidential and sensitive information by resorting to digital transmission considered as a safer channel for transmitting the relevant order. The documents containing information are related to the competent authorities by the national members of the Eurojust via the national desks which establish a more secure channel of communication for the respective national authorities and in good practice allowing the necessary information to be transmitted in a timely manner according to the right channels in a confidential, precise manner.

¹⁷<https://www.Eurojust.europa.eu/it/publication/report-Eurojust-casework-european-investigation-order>

Article 6, par. 1, letter. b) of the Directive and the case of the Irish desk

Art. 6, par. 1, letter. b) of the Directive is oriented towards the equivalence clause with regard to specific investigative measures. In particular par. 1 of art. 6 of the Directive in relation to the Irish desk, provides:

“(...) as a condition for issuing the EIO, that the requested act or acts are permitted in an internal similar case (...)”.

The aforementioned provision has been addressed on the initiative of the Irish desk which, in September 2018, asked some questions to the other national desks, summarized in the report together with the answers obtained. The need was nevertheless felt to delve deeper into some aspects relating to the conditions for issuing an EIO, which may give rise to operational difficulties. It was asked whether, on the basis of Art. 6 § 1 letter. b) of the Directive, the issuing judicial authority should or should not be competent, according to the *lex fori*, to carry out the investigative measure requested from the foreign authority. Different approaches emerged about it. Eight desks specified that, in their respective states of origin, the provision contained in the Directive has been interpreted in the sense that the issuing authority must necessarily have the competence to order the investigative measure also at national level¹⁸.

¹⁸<https://www.Eurojust.europa.eu/it/publication/report-Eurojust-casework-european-investigation-order>

As a consequence from what we read, the issuing of the EIO did not affect the nature and powers of the authority where the issuing or authorization of the order was issued.

In speciem, according to the report of the 2020:

“(…) three desks responded that, in their respective systems, the provision of art. 6 § 1 letter. b) is not interpreted as meaning that the issuing authority must have the necessary competence to adopt the same measure according to national law (…)”.

The identification of the competent authorities for this purpose is independent, in fact, from the existence of the powers to adopt the same investigative acts in a similar internal case, based, rather, on the procedural stage in which the issuing of the order takes place. This is requested from the national desks if the respective legislations attributed to certain authorities the competence to issue the EIO relating to the performance of one or more specific investigative acts referred to in the list contained in section “C” of Annex “A” and, if so, whether or not the choice reflected the spectrum of powers conferred at national level. Only four desks responded in the affirmative, specifying that the criteria most commonly used to identify the competent authority to order the adoption of a specific investigative measure consist in the type and nature of the measure (essentially, whether or not less coercive), as well as at the stage in which the proceedings are¹⁹.

¹⁹<https://www.Eurojust.europa.eu/it/publication/report-Eurojust-casework-european-investigation-order>

It is clear from the Irish experience that the new Directive has not affected a reduction in the role of the Prosecutor but has affected compliance with the rogatory system with a significant reduction in the powers assigned to this body.

Eurojust and its role in complex and multilateral procedures

The function of the execution of investigative orders of a bilateral nature was based on Regulation no. 2018/1727/EU²⁰ and especially to art. 2, par. 1 which concerned cross-border cooperation, i.e. multilateral for Member States and also for third countries. Organizational meetings, coordination centers, guarantees of execution of multiple orders or other instruments of judicial cooperation even in the face of pending proceedings and procedures that were connected in different states puts Eurojust at an embryonic stage of the relevant procedures but in an advantageous way. The issuing authority could invoke the assistance of the EUACJC to get in touch with the foreign authority, thus preparing a joint action for the relative carrying out of searches, involving and allowing the carrying out of the execution of the necessity that each national desk received further information and contained in the EIO reaching the search warrant from the judge within the deadlines. The relevant

²⁰Regulation (EU) 2018/1727 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 November 2018 on the European Union Agency for Criminal Justice Cooperation (Eurojust), and replacing and repealing Council Decision 2002/187/JHA, PE/37/2018/REV/1, OJ L 295, 21.11.2018, p. 138–183.

response from the competent authority after 12 days allowed the executing authority to prepare the relevant documentation and submit it to the competent judge. Thus in a specific way:

“(…) only formal changes to the original version of the order, integrated with the requested information, would have been accepted”.

The issuing authority sent the documentation to the relevant desk, which took care of translating it into English that same night

“(…) with the translation attached, it was immediately forwarded to the executing authority, which confirmed its once received five minutes before the deadline expired (…)”.

A further request for clarification was received, which required a response within an hour. The national desk immediately contacted the prosecutor in charge of the investigations, and then communicated his answers to the executing authority. Another request was forwarded aimed at acquiring additional information, to which the desk responded promptly (Martin, Manuel, Yamuza, 2020).

According to the above we understand that Eurojust was the precursor to the authorization for the search and to a successfully operation from an investigative point of view. Thus the authorities carried out the house search where the outcome allowed the relative seizure of laptops, iPads, USB sticks, mobile phones, etc., everything that was necessary for the purchase of information concerning bank accounts and commercial contracts.

Can we therefore speak for a good outcome of investigations and effective results? And what are the parameters of success?

We cannot answer yes or no, but we can say that there are parameters that we must take into consideration. First of all, we consider the purchase of a test that is located in a specific state and when comes from multiple states. The role of the Eurojust is based on coordination dealing with the enforcement phase and the sharing of evidence between the requesting states and without the related prejudice to the investigations. On the one hand, the coordination of the enforcement phase and the sharing of evidence between the requesting states is detrimental to the investigations. Thus it is agreed to future requests to each state without specifying, indicating the relationship that exists between the EIO and the ongoing proceedings of the other state. A second questionable case is that of evidentiary seizure and the amount of computer data after transmission to the issuing authority. Thus the authorities involving other states and issuing the relevant investigative orders for the acquisition of the information documentation were already seized. The issuing authority thus made the seizure request and the executive authority sent the relevant copies of the material obtained through the first EIO to the other Member States. In this case the ongoing coordination and the coordination meetings which

concerned the creation of an investigative team and after the execution of an EIO, or a rogatory letter had as their objective the intensification of cooperation between the authorities involved. A team will be legitimate if it starts from the observation that the establishing agreements contain the relevant ad hoc clause for the evidence collected through the EIO or the rogatory letter and they fall within the application area of the same agreement.

Another, final aspect that had to do with the necessary identification, demanding of the most suitable authority to prosecute new and/or perhaps different crimes that are the result of the execution of the order that has to do with the authority which transmits several EIOs to the address of multiple states. This type of cooperation establishes a lively coordination where time is very important and especially for investigations through authorities that prevent reaching an agreement on jurisdictional issues. The executive phase highlights various differences between the relative measures adopted, especially in terms of the reconstruction of the relevant facts which are the subject of each proceeding. The involvement of Eurojust from the opening of the investigations makes it possible to remedy the negative defects of coordination and the related problems that certainly enter the jurisdiction sector.

Deprivation of liberty, transfer of prisoners and issuing state. Are these problems or actual solutions?

The temporary transfer of prisoners identifies the cooperation instrument that is used in the sector of the EIO that deals with the failure to arrest, the legitimate deprivation of personal liberty in the issuing state. Another non-comparable aspect concerns the prison authorities who refused to subject a measure to restrictive measures and in the absence of an arrest warrant. In this case we note that the majority judges used and held that:

“(...) Art. 22 § 6 of the EIO Directive does not constitute a sufficient legal basis to justify the deprivation of personal liberty of the person temporarily transferred from one state to another (...)”.

Eurojust suggested that the executing authority should explicitly ask the issuing authority for maintenance of detention during the stay of the transferred person in the territory of the state of destination²¹. In reality, the elapsed period of issue for the interested party who must serve in the territory of the executing state is that established by Art. 22, par. 7 of the Directive also allows and raises problems for the detained person thus offering the relevant transfer which revokes consent when he is in the territory of the state carrying out an act of investigation within its borders. The lack of consent, even legitimate, as well as the refusal of execution is sent to Art. 22, par. 2, letter. a) of the Directive.

²¹CJEU, C-314/18, SFSF (Mandat d'arrêt européen-Garantie de renvoi dans l'État d'exécution) of 10 March 2020, ECLI:EU:C:2020:191, published in the electronic Reports of the cases.

The case of judicial coordination operations and collaboration with the police

Cover operations are investigations that are thought to be more at a national level than the coordination that is carried out between police forces and judicial authorities. Exceptions are noted in the conclusion of bilateral agreements that seek to exempt the obligation to resort to the EIO and/or the request that would be necessary for the desks that some states have specified that undercover operations are managed at the level of police cooperation and reserved under the orders of the prosecutor where the power to decide and accept some investigations require the acceptance and requests for contribution of infiltrated agents.

Cooperation of this type has as its consequence the status of the person to be examined, perhaps also via videoconference, and the location or locations of the examination.

The difficulties are focused on practical and technical aspects relating to the status of the person and the taking of declarations for carrying out the first hearing. The identification of the Eurojust channel to prevent and clarify the related misunderstandings regarding information that was insufficient, incorrect or based on wrong translations. All these misunderstandings were part of the procedural process of a complex proceeding. The issuing authority is a bit particular on

the other hand. It did not indicate the questions that had to ask in each witness. Finally, the participation of a judicial or police authority was not specified. These are arguments that we have seen in practice as well as underlining the important role that Eurojust plays without wasting any more time and/or throwing up dates for hearings due to impediments or unavailability of witnesses.

Not only the prosecutor's office or the police station collaborate with the Eurojust but also the EUACJC when faced with complex situations which also involved the hearing of video conferences due to a flood of suspects or witnesses, as well as investigations in locations belonging to different jurisdictions that according to Art. 21 of the Directive are connected to the execution supported by the state receiving the order. If, however, the executing authority deems them exceptionally high, it can evaluate, together with the issuing one, the distribution of expenses or the modification of the content of the EIO. The issuing authority had explicitly requested that the hearing take place in the presence of an interpreter, which would have entailed a significant increase in execution costs. The issuing authority was willing to take on the payment of the interpreter's costs²².

²²CJEU, C-324/17, Gavanozov of 24 October 2019, ECLI:EU:C:2019:892, published in the electronic Reports of the cases.

We can affirm from what we read above that the work of the national authorities is difficult to find in agreement with the subjects who had to be subjected to the hearing. The issuing authorities are also against changing the qualification of the executing authority thus causing difficulties in the refusal to recognize Eurojust's attempts at resolving mediations as a filter of procedural work for the acquisition of criminal evidence. On the other hand, there is also the problem of different procedural rights which are referred to the various Member States, thus putting in danger that the alleged perpetrator of a crime could also hold the position of the suspect or accused. The existence of different interpretations where the content of the law continues to remain silent or making use of the right against self-incrimination still makes it difficult to acquire the bank details of a company under investigation for money laundering where the author is unknown. The executing authorities which gave as a privilege the right against self-incrimination provided for by national law could prevent the relevant conduct of the examination considering the risk that the person under examination reveals a potential suspect. On the other hand, the issue that the *lex fori* also recognizes the right to remain under examination in the face of a concrete risk makes the declarations to be characterized as self-providing, including in this specific case that every subject in the capacity of witness must know a

priori who has the right not to respond.

We clearly speak for an open dialogue and exchange of information between the authorities that allow to satisfy the relevant requests for cooperation, guarantee and respect of the rights recognized to the people who are involved in the investigations. The executive authority had to provide for the participation of the lawyer in the witness examination as well as the reasons for this stage to the relevant subject, making the refusal to proceed according to the formalities indicated by the issuing authority and the related behaviors which risk the order to break and overcome mutual trust between the countries of the Union.

A specific area of interception with or without technical assistance from another Member State

What is surprising is that a large part of the report focused on the sector of telephone interception did not distinguish the relevance of a technical collaboration with another Member State where according to Art. 30 of the Directive:

“(…) problems encountered can be linked, once again, to the divergences existing at national level (about the scope of application of the interceptions, the purposes of using the related results, the duration of the operations, the status of person subjected to the interceptions) and the insufficiency of the information provided by the issuing authority (...) as a legal basis for issuing an “environmental” interception order, through the covert installation of bugs in the place where communications between those present take place. This is a particularly delicate issue, which arises again, as will be said shortly, also in the context of interceptions that do not require technical assistance from

others (...)”²³.

As regards the relative status of the person who was to be subjected to wiretaps, the major problem concerned the possibility that the communications of a person under investigation did not qualify as a suspect. Thus according to the *lex loci*, the interceptions of the person who holds the status of informed person relating to the facts that are more stringent respect the same hypothesis, i.e. that the state of execution where the interception of the communications of a potential witness is prohibited except there is a main reason for the decision that the subject can come into contact with the suspect or transmit messages on his/her behalf.

These problems for the related interceptions allow the executing state not to proceed but to remain faithful to Art. 30, par. 5 of the Directive where the execution of an interception order can refuse the related requested act which is not permitted but only in an internal case and by analogy. The principle of equivalence and the use of the results of interceptions by the authorities of the issuing state have as a consequence the limitation of the investigative purposes, i.e. the related intelligence purposes, not to continue to an extension for testing purposes such as evidence purposes. In EUACJC, from an objective point of view, the implementation methods between telephone and/or telematic

²³<https://www.Eurojust.europa.eu/it/publication/report-Eurojust-casework-european-investigation-order>

interception, i.e. wiretapping-interception of communication by telephone or other telecommunication technology; interception through conversations between those present: bugging-installation of a small microphone in the place to be bugged and transmission to some nearby receiver, are the results of the products that also remain hidden elements for communications or conversations and the typologies interfere as a measure where the right confidentiality is violated and the asymmetries created especially in individual states are affected by the application practice leading to the fact that a positive and unequivocal solution is the result of concrete, precise regulatory data and the related result obtained.

Ultimately, we can say that the issue remains difficult even at a national level despite the continuous reforms at an internal level due to the fact that the regulation of wiretapping, especially at home level, i.e. of the so-called “trojan horse” as an investigative tool of a concrete use permitted in all countries adhering to the Directive in question.

Article 31 of the Directive and Annex C)

Art. 31 of the Directive has to do with interceptions relating to technical assistance²⁴. The same Directive provides for the

²⁴The Eurojust report affirms that: “(...) such interceptions do not fall so much within the general scope of the directive, since there is no “order” to be executed, but rather within the specific context of art. 31, which draws up a system based on the notifications to be made through attachment “C” (...)”.

relevant notification obligation for operations against the state where the territory is in use and the communication address of the interested person to be carried out via the form of the attachment C). The lack of use by the authority of the state of interception according to the attached form C) and the failure to indicate useful information for the notified state arise and enter into the circle of problems of authorization provision where the duration of the operations foreseen by the relative *lex fori*, as well as the moment in which he became aware of the movement abroad of the subject who is under the interception regime. We are faced with the issues that include the equivalence clause if not everything works and we proceed according to Art. 31, par. 3 of the Directive where failure to comply may lead to a ban on the start of operations or interruption already started²⁵.

Thus avoiding other problems relating to the intrusion on other decisions, it seems that the adoption by the recipient authority of the order or of the relevant notification is a flexible and collaborative attitude, thus presupposing an exposure of the elements that support the relevant foreign request also through subsequent additions. Clarifying that flexibility and

²⁵According to Art. 30 § 4 and the section: “H7” of annex “A”: “(...) interceptions without technical assistance the directive does not require the authority of the state of interception to indicate “the reasons why it considers the requested investigative document useful for the criminal proceedings concerned, Annex “C” being limited to providing for the generic indication of all the necessary information” to allow the authority of the notified state to verify compliance with the principle of equivalence (...)”.

collaboration does not mean passive acquiescence to the relative claims relating to the foreign authority but guarantees of the people who ensure the national systems. There are many reasons for this and they are oriented towards the legitimation of forms of cooperation based on superficial and very hasty assessments where mutual trust is nourished by respect for fundamental rights by each Member State. We are not talking about trust but about meticulous checks that do not compromise relationships according to customs and perspectives of the *do ut des* type.

Covid and work of the EIO

The responses provided by various Member States during the pandemic²⁶ allow us to say and call into question that Eurojust and the European Judicial Network through the coordination of the European Council have put some tables and a summary topic dating back to 12 February 2021²⁷ reporting to related instruments of judicial cooperation in criminal matters including those crimes which the EU has mainly dealt with since the beginning, i.e. European arrest warrant, extradition, European investigation order, legal assistance, transfer of convicted persons, seizure and confiscation of assets, joint investigations

²⁶These are Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Iceland, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Norway, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden and Hungary.

²⁷See, The impact of COVID-19 on judicial cooperation in criminal matters- Executive summary of information compiled by Eurojust and EJM.

teams. The general considerations that are carried out in the executive summary lead to responses provided by various states, thus selecting a level of detail for the peculiarity of the content. The main difficulties concerned the execution sector, especially of the first months of the pandemic where the judicial cooperation activity was examined and followed in an overall manner due to the health emergency. In the issuing procedures and the execution of the EIO, the rogatory letters were restrictive and forced towards measures to contain the spread of the contagion given the criteria introduced, the tools in one's hands continuing the electronic channels in a faster way guaranteeing compliance with the measures for holding hearings and exams in person.

In practice, Luxembourg:

“(...) reported the difficulty of carrying out house searches, due to the closure of the majority of companies and offices in the territory, and the lack of assistance from foreign police forces (...)”.

In the case of Poland and Portugal the health emergency was based on suspensive measures and the execution of EIO and of rogatory letters were active only for urgent cases and after precise identification and case-by-case evaluation of the concrete elements they had in hand. Bulgaria announced:

“(...) possible delays in the execution of all EIOs, due to limited judicial and police resources, also communicating the deferral of non-urgent EIOs until the end of the state of emergency declared by the national authorities (...)”.

Estonia opted for a case-by-case approach, making known its intention to give priority to the execution of measures not

involving direct physical contact. Latvia:

“(…) made use of a criterion anchored to the phase of the procedure (pre-trial or trial stage), specifying that the execution of activities involving physical contact would take place only where deemed strictly necessary, in consideration of the seriousness of the crime, maintaining a distance of two meters and prohibiting the participation of the issuing authorities (…).”

As regards the case of Germany the Federal States have adopted some functional criteria to establish a hierarchy of procedures to be carried out as a matter of priority, such as the existence of a particular public interest or the importance of the case, the state of detention of the suspect or accused, the danger of dispersion of the evidence, the imminent statute of limitations or the seriousness of the crime, the risk of worsening of the investigations and, the urgency and type of the measure requested. The execution was not limited to urgent cases only, despite the fact that some physiological delays and postponements occurred, sometimes also due to technical difficulties, especially in the case of remote hearings. It prevented both the presence on the national territory of foreign police and the participation of German officials abroad.

Hungary:

“(…) while ensuring the execution of EIOs and rogatory letters regardless of the urgency, it recommended not ordering the appearance of people before the authorities, deeming methods that allow remote examination preferable. The increase in hearings via videoconference during the lockdown was also recorded by Romania (…).”

Equally important was the case of Malta:

“(…) which made the execution depend on the type of measure requested, on the urgency and on the existence of a public interest, in the face of the closure

of the courts and the suspension of legal deadlines (...). The urgency of the procedure could also be established at a later time, following an exchange between the authorities, and that the house searches continued to take place adopting the necessary health precautions (...)."

Sweden stated that it had not received instructions on whether to limit the execution of EIOs, nor had it adopted priority criteria for their issuance. Italy, France and Spain have asserted that they have not encountered, in principle, any particular obstacles when issuing and executing EIOs and rogatory letters. Spain communicated:

"(...) the regular carrying out of judicial cooperation activity in the evidentiary field, both from the active and passive side, without the need to issue specific guidelines. However, difficulties were encountered in carrying out investigative measures involving the transfer of people or other types of physical contact. In relation to the house searches, it was deemed appropriate to proceed with a concrete assessment, in order to prevent judicial officials from exposing themselves to the risk of contagion, in violation of the restrictions imposed at national level (...)."

It is noted that in cases of urgency it was a concrete line used and granted to the EIOs especially for the reasons of the issuing authority. The transmission channels that are used have specified that they have followed the electronic route, orders and requests to the competent authorities that serve the addresses for the response of the relevant questionnaire included in the "Atlas" platform without the need for the central authority. Within this context only Latvia stated that: "having contacted the central authorities via email only in urgent cases", while Slovakia requested that, in such cases, the EIO and other requests forwarded in digital format should follow the sending

by ordinary mail of the original paper copy. Finally, the activation of contact points at Eurojust and the EJM was expressly requested (by Italy, Finland, Portugal, the Czech Republic and Slovenia), which however remains left to the discretion of the prosecuting judicial authority.

The pandemic period demonstrated a very broad collaborative spirit which was based on the favor cooperationis and the principle of mutual recognition guided by the principle of proportionality and the Directive itself. The specificity of the cases, the ongoing research, the right balance between law and health as well as the investigative and evidentiary needs have shaped a series of very susceptible criteria returning and establishing a continuous dialogue between the authorities abroad and also moving toward a higher spirit as was traced by the European legislator by comparing it in the end with the attitude of obstructionism outside the context of the health emergency and coming into play and above all with the fundamental rights and first of all the right of defence.

Concluding remarks

What can we say and understand so far from what we have studied from the Eurojust report and the discussions we have followed in the previous paragraphs?

First of all, the Directive of the EIO has played an important and

leading role from the beginning, first of all for the harmonization and creation of sophisticated, technical, concrete and precise mechanisms for the rapprochement of national criminal procedural legislation. The supranational legislation is always under discussion on general principles where with an enormous degree of elasticity it shows that the cases adopted in a concrete way play a similar role which favors the formation of a previous European panorama as well as a parallel accomplice with the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU). Within this context, the canonical principle of proportionality as well as the tools it involves, based on the 2014 Directive, arrives at a reasonable balance that accompanies adequate support for the investigative needs and fundamental guarantees of the person. The lack of unitary of the European legislation on evidence which also includes the rights of the people involved in cooperation procedures seems to be an operational reality of the investigation order as a purpose of ascertaining the facts and above all of the exercise of criminal prosecution, of the collection of evidence found abroad and that of defense.

The sums of the results are still neutral. We cannot talk about positive or negative results but only about a certain enthusiasm, because first of all we know what the relative problems are. The work of the prosecutor's team is enormous. There are many uncertainties as we also noted in the relevant Report of the

Eurojust, especially in our opinion on interceptions. But maybe this isn't the case at the national level too. The technical complexity, the regulatory divergences, the contradictory elements, the haste for the conclusion of the investigations, the lack of trust towards the interlocutor abroad, the lax attitudes are some of the elements that cause the results to lose their initial aim as well as the methods used to achieve them. The imposition of the *lex fori* and the related obstacle to cooperation are in contrast with the logic of mutual recognition and mutual trust between the states belonging to the Union. There is an expression of the principle of mutual recognition, i.e. the extremity of the absence which prompts the relative investigative haste by relying on the *lex loci*. Full mutual recognition that is quite different from the inspiration behind the birth of the Directive becomes a counterproductive argument. Why? Perhaps due to the efficiency that drives the acceptance of compromises, as well as the use abroad of the result of the impossibility of using the process of evidence collected through methods that do not respect the essential core of the guarantees of the *lex fori*. This remains a topic, or rather a main reason where the discipline of the EIO allows an implementation of mutual recognition of a tempered, not full nature and with the aim of encouraging the meeting of wills coming from procedural systems that present abstract and unsurpassable profiles

allowing the acquisition of evidentiary and effective material in the process established according to national law.

According to the spirit of the Directive the attitude is halfway because the attitude should be common to all authorities who are involved in an issuing and execution procedure in the investigative order. In practice, the issuing authority demands the relative observance of the procedural guarantees where the violation is covered by the specific sanction in the national law completing thus the investigation order which is forwarded abroad. The recipient authority which is guided by the principle of proportionality evaluates the indications received and also takes into consideration the replacement of the *lex fori* and the *lex loci* such as the refusal to recognize and/or execute the order also justifying the need to safeguard the fundamental principles of the law of the executing state.

The ascertained failure to comply with the proportional fee and fundamental rights by the issuing authority has as its final objective the prevention of recognition and execution of the order. The receiving authority hesitates to oppose its refusal, overcoming the fear of altering the relative balance of relations with the issuing foreign country and of facing the rejection of a possible request for collaboration with reversed parties. That is, a practice that responds to the utilitarian logic of the *do ut des* ready to accommodate other claims that remain insensitive, even

negative in terms of defensive guarantees.

The inevitable intensification of criminal judicial cooperation between the states of the EU and the digitalisation of crimes lead national authorities to commit the related activity of research and acquisition of evidence beyond national borders which does not appear to follow the rhythms of investigative efficiency but as observance of the fundamental rights that are inherent to the person as a result of defense. This is another effort in the face of the impediments that nourish the Directive of the EIO where the verification of the effective respect of proportionality is a conduct where the issuing and executing authorities follow direct and constant dialogue through the authorities and the auxiliary role of the Eurojust which conducts an act different or less intrusive than the one originally requested and is in accordance with the principle of proportionality. The use of refusal relating to the violation of fundamental rights is considered as a last resort where the consultations have had a positive outcome. Thus a relative remedy of an abstract but efficient harmonization of guarantees is agreed upon.

The criminal investigation order is a newborn instrument that penetrates the fabric of European judicial cooperation at an ever-uphill prospect. Jurisprudential practice will be a use for the tools offered by the supranational legislator, conferring the relative guarantees for the defense and the relative weight of the

results of the investigations. The first step has been taken, the ground is certainly fertile for sowing a judicial culture of a supranational nature in living law as an idea of European inspiration where fundamental rights cannot unjustly sacrifice the altar to an efficiency and investigative approach of an inseparable union where one exists for the other. Perhaps this is the spirit we will concentrate on in the next few years, i.e. for new steps in the European investigation order and with positive results in favor of European justice and the harmonization of European cooperation and criminal justice.

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